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Teachers' attitude towards assessment on learners' environmental activities performance in public pre-primary schools in Nandi County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT

The continual and swift reforms in the education system in Kenya are brought due to the societal demands. The aim of this study is to ascertain whether there is a connection between attitudes of teachers towards assessment on learner's environmental activities performance. A teacher with teaching assessment strategies and furthermore with his attitude and behaviours, provides his learners to gain a mentally healthy personality and to have a new clear world view by leaving unforgettable traces on them. This study sought to uncover how attitude of teachers affect performances of learners. In this sense, this paper provides a clear understanding of education and dynamics of relationship between teacher's attitude and learner's environmental activities performance. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The target population comprised of 919 public pre-primary schools comprising of 1,829 pre-primary teachers in Nandi County, Kenya. Stratified and simple random sampling methods were used to select schools and teachers for the study. Through this method 160 teachers were selected for the study. Data collection utilized questionnaire. Reliability of the instruments was determined through split half technique. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as means, percentages and frequencies. The study revealed that most teachers adopted the assessment for learning strategy in assessing learners. Most of the teachers had not gone back for training to be acquainted in the Competence Based Curriculum thus having a challenge in the new modes of assessing learners towards the acquisition of competencies and skills. It also revealed that motivation should be enhanced among pre-primary teachers for them to deliver assessment procedures and lastly administrators support should be paramount so that teachers' service delivery in terms of assessment is not hampered. The paper recommends that for successful Competence Based Curriculum assessment results in terms of learners' attainment of competencies and skills in the learning areas, the government through the Ministry of Education should ensure that all pre-primary school stakeholders play their roles maximally to ensure that teachers' attitude and service deliver on assessment of pre-primary school learners are well catered for.

KEYWORDS

Competence based curriculum, attitude, training, pre-primary, assessment, strategy, environmental activities.

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Background to the Study

Assessment is a strategy through which teachers and learners are introduced to the results achieved during the teaching and learning process. Assessment is applied with the intention of identifying the level of the learners' knowledge to initiate the learners learning. Assessment assists teachers to get feedback about the learner's level of knowledge in environmental activities. It also guides them to the steps that have to be undertaken to improve their knowledge, (Bransford et.al, 2000).

Many issues are critical to a learner's success in institutions of learning. Assessment is one of those vital factors. The fact is that in all teaching and learning processes, learners' assessment is an inevitable construct that elicit and sustains effective learning. Assessment has long been recognized as maintaining a central position in learners learning. Practices of assessment have a powerful influence on learning behavior of learners because offering various assessment methods is often recommended as good practice in response to numerous critiques of the over-reliance on traditional tests. The reason behind this is that, the use of techniques which more appropriately assess different kinds of learning processes, the need to cater for differences individual learner learning preferences and styles and the need to enhance learning psychological approaches of learning, (Torrance, 2005).

Schools are established for the purpose of teaching and learning. In order to ascertain whether or not learning has taken place, teachers have to evaluate learners. This process of evaluating learners' is what is referred to as assessment being a process by which a teacher gathers information about the outcomes of his or her teaching and uses the outcomes for further improvement (Yoloye, 2009). In other words assessment is a vital tool for the sustainability of good performance as well as an authentic tool for the improvement of poor outcomes.

Assessing children's performance is one of the most vital aspects of the activities of a teacher. It is therefore vital for teachers to have knowledge about how learners' performance is assessed and which techniques are employed in assessing learner's performance. In addition, it is important that teachers follow to change on the assessment techniques and practices due to the changes in the curriculum.

According to Uzun&Ertok(2020), In Turkey, educational system, summative assessment approach or traditional assessment approach was the most one used in the past. In the last five years, it was seen that these assessment types were less effective in education in order to the recent developments and demands in science and society since learning approach is changed, it affects assessment procedures and approaches. Since the current views of learning and instructions in schools that emphasize learner-centred, constructive teaching and learning require assessment systems to be change to "go with" the content and style of teaching and learning experiences by the learner. The vital reason of change in assessment practices Turkish educational system is due to education reforms in the world and Turkey is emphasizing the teaching assessment of higher-level cognitive skills.

In the United States of America Department of Education in 2002 indicated the importance of implementing competency-based initiatives in schools and colleges (US Department of Education, National Center for Educational Statistics, 2002). Competency based curriculum summarizes academic and professional profiles, defines new objectives in the learning process, enhances learning environments and shifts the concept of learning as accumulation of knowledge to learning as a permanent attitude towards knowledge acquisition (Edwards & Sanchez-Diaz, 2009).

In Mexico the implementation of CBC began in Mexico in 2009 through a number of reforms on basic education and national education policies where the skills, values, attitude and knowledge were to be applied in day to day activities and learners were required to reflect on their endeavors.

Competence was viewed as the application of skills, knowledge, values and attitudes (Castillo, 2011). In China it was found out that teachers were not seen as crucial to the intent and action of the curriculum (Jin & Li, 2011). Wang examined the translation of policies into practice and found out that it did not focus on educators as critical stakeholders in the implementation process (Wang, 2010).

Education in Ethiopia has achieved incredible progress over the past two decades with primary school attendance rates quadrupling. But the attendance is only one piece of improving education results. The quality of education must also be given ample attention, especially when less than half of all primary schools learners are passing their end-of-year exams, and only four percent of Grade 2 learners can proficiently read. (NAEA, 2016). The government has set a goal to create a new learning generation for the country. They understand that improving the learning of children will generate enhanced abilities, ultimately leading to the growth of the nation.

One key initiative led by UNICEF and the Ministry of Education (MoE) is Assessment for Learning (AfL) where teachers are equipped with skills, resources and a supporting environment to shift their teaching approaches to become more active, continuous, competency based and engaging for learners with an ultimate goal of improving learning outcomes.

According to Heubert & Hauser (1999), global evidence demonstrates a strong link between formative classroom assessment and better learners learning outcomes. After teachers implement AfL techniques, the learners' achievement tests improve significantly. Unfortunately, this has not been the standard practice in Ethiopia because teachers assess their learners with simple tests repeated throughout the year that do not reference the national Minimum Learning Competencies (MLC). In addition, the final scores include high percentages from non-learning categories like attendance rates, staff participation and cleanness to boost their averages so that all learners would pass. The results do not reflect the learners learning levels, creating a gap in skill development of children as well as in teachers understanding of learners levels throughout the year.

Assessment for Learning places real-time information gathering at the centre of the interventions so that teaching is better informed, lesson planning is better prepared and much support is given to children. With Assessment for Learning, teachers rethink how they teach by placing the learner's progress at the heart of everything they do. But real learning can only be achieved if a system of teachers, school administrators and government counterparts invest in strategies to improve the quality of teaching.

According to Mukunja, (2015), the implementation of CBC requires the use of new assessment methods be aligned with the new curriculum (CBC). To implement changes brought about by the new assessment methods, it is necessary that pre-primary teachers develop a positive attitude become knowledgeable and better equipped with new alternative approaches to assessment of pre-primary learners. It is therefore, out of this notion that the researcher wanted to find out teachers attitude towards assessment on learners environmental activities performance in public pre-primary in Nandi County, Kenya.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching is an endeavour that requires adequate training. It involves performing work within the teaching framework with dedication and enthusiasm to ensure that the goals and objectives are being achieved. This informs that the teacher is a pivot of any education system in any level of learning. The teacher is the one in charge of the teaching and learning process within an instructional environment

i.e. inside and outside the classroom. Teachers have a great task of making learners' competent and resourceful in the society where they come from. Teachers are regarded as the pillars of the nation because they are in charge of the whole round development of learners who can steer the country's development. The teacher being a good role model, it makes the learners look up to them and therefore, they should have a positive attitude towards the learners without taking into account their variations in creed, tribe, age, background etc. This will also enhance a positive attitude towards assessment of the child in order for them to acquire all the competencies in environmental activities within the pre-school environment both inside and outside the classroom.

Assessments are used to gather information about a child's progress. If one uses observation as a form of assessment, on its own it is like a photograph, it can only record what is happening at that specific point of time. As such single observations are not enough for any professional to decide whether or not a child is making progress and developing skills.

Teachers assess learners' needs to help them with initial advice and guidance and to help them design programmes they teach. Assessment is also an integral part of teaching systems, of learning support systems.

The success of schools at all levels is determined by the academic performance of its learners and for any schools to be considered academically sound, it must put in place strategies to promote learners learning and better performance. One of these strategies is, through the use of varied assessment techniques enhanced by teacher's attitude.

Due to the changes in technological advancement in the 21st century which requires the acquisition of varied competencies among the learners in order for one to fit in the job market, it is therefore necessary for teachers to carry up to date assessment among the learners to ensure the acquisitions of right knowledge, skills, attitudes and values.

Thus, it was essential to conduct a study to investigate teachers' attitude towards assessment on learners' environmental activities performance and to bring the attention of pre-primary stakeholders' gaps which may be in the assessment process. Knowledge of the above would enhance designing of intervention strategies like teachers motivation and administrators support that would enhance a positive teachers attitude towards assessment that facilitate successful implementation of necessary assessment strategies of the pre-primary school environmental activities.

Objectives

The research objectives were to establish strategies used by teachers in assessing on learners; teachers training level towards assessment; teachers' motivation as a factor which affect the teachers' attitude towards assessment and the support provided by administrators towards assessment on learners' environmental activities performance in public pre-schools in Nandi County, Kenya.

Literature Review

According to the Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (2008), assessment is vital to the education process. In schools they are used to measure what learners have learnt at the end of a unit, to promote learners, to make sure they have met the necessary standards on the way to earning certification for preschool completion or to enter certain occupations or as a strategy for choosing learners for entry into further education.

According to Carnoy (1999), Education discourse moves along the lines of global change and therefore assumes various methods at different times in history guided by divergent ideologies. Nations are no longer the only formulators of their policies. The current global policy convergence is due to the fact that different institutions operating at different levels transfer from norms and policies that govern the world (Ball, 1998). At the turn of the 21st century a new discourse succeed in education namely Competency Based Curriculum (Soare, 2015).

According to Wheelahan, (2012), Competency Based Curriculum has shaped the way in which knowledge is conceived and as a result has also altered pedagogic practices. The attention on teaching practices in Competency Based Curriculum is now oriented towards promoting self-actualization rather than acquisition of knowledge. This has led to teachers paying minimal attention to knowledge access and provision.

Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) recommended that, reporting in formative assessment should be frequent and ongoing communication between the teacher and the learner, and with the parents about the progress the learner was making towards meeting the curriculum outcomes. The reporting should focus on a series or cluster of learning (KICD, 2017). KICD also suggested that, at different points during the year, this portfolio could be used to discuss with the learner regarding their progress as well as with parents, administrators or other staff members providing services for learners. Teachers should be honest, fair and provide sufficient detail and contextual information. They need to keep detailed records of various components of assessment with descriptions of what each component of the assessment measured, accuracy, against the criteria and learning outcomes and supporting evidence. Learners' ability is rated in terms of whether they are exceeding expectation(80 - 100%), meeting expectation (65 - 79%), approaching expecting (50 - 64%), and below expectation (0 - 49%). A remark against the rating provided is then provided.

According to Akin, (2009), education being the greatest hope of a nation especially for a developing country likes Kenya; it cannot just be left in the hands of personnel who have no interest in the teaching profession. Therefore, the transfer of knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another requires the services of persons who are well trained and skilled in the teaching profession. Such individual are teachers. They are assigned the role of transmitting the accumulated knowledge skills and competencies from one generation to the next. This is due to the fact that, preschool education forms the foundation years for all other academic levels. Therefore, it is a very vital stage in a child's academic, social, emotional and physical development. Therefore, there is need to remember about the developmental status of young children, i.e. the developing state of their attention and the self-regulation abilities that lead to assessment being challenging than in other people (Shepard et. al, 1998).

The learner must show their ability to work through particular units of competency utilizing the standards offered by educational standards in order to establish their competence. Competence based training focuses on the learner's capacity to receive, respond and understand information while applying their abilities and knowledge consistently (Sistermans, 2020).

According to Frost et al., (2015), learning outcomes in Competency Based Curriculum emphasize competencies that include application and creation of knowledge, along with the development of important skills and dispositions. Mosha (2012), also pointed out that a curriculum that is competency-based, contains the specific outcome of statements that show the competencies to

be acquired by the learners during the learning process, that is, result outcome behaviours or tasks, conditions for their performance, and acceptable standards are shared with the learners.

According to Early Years Foundation Stage Guidance (2008), children are competent learners from birth and develop and learn in a wide variety of ways. All practitioners should, therefore, look carefully at children in their care, consider their needs, interests and stages of development and use all of this information to help plan a challenging and enjoyable experience across all the areas of learning and development.

Amy (2013), natural materials have very high play value and contribute to all major areas of development. As resources for play they are entirely open-ended and can be used in a myriad of different ways. Guy (2012), added that, Early Years Foundation Stage children learn and develop well in enabling environments, in which their experiences respond to their individual needs and there is a strong partnership between practitioners and parents and careers.

The concept of attitude entails an individual's way of thinking, acting, or behaving (Pransky & Bailey, 2009). According to a study carried out in Nigeria by Bandura, the attitude has marked implications on the learner, the teacher, and the immediate social groups. The attitude of the teacher towards the student will also affect how he or she will interact with the whole system of an academic institution. Other studies by Baker and Crist (1981) and several others have also suggested that learners develop certain attitudes and behaviors towards learning because of the learning experiences and the teaching environment (Pransky and Bailey, 2009; Baker and Crist, 1981).

Baker and Crist (1981) further assert that a certain attitude in learners may be instilled or learned simply by following what the teacher does either through his/her opinion. This is because learners regard teachers as their example and role model. Thus, learners tend to mimic or imitate what the teacher does or how he or she behaves, which ultimately has marked effects on the learning situation. Therefore in this respect, the learners' attitudes are drawn from the teachers' dispositions which are used to form their attitudes that have a likely effect on the learners' learning outcomes (Baker and Crist, 1981; Pransky and Bailey, 2009).

According to Howard & Del Rosario (2000), culturally responsive teaching involves a kind of teaching where teachers are more acquainted with the world of the children and attempt to offer better opportunities for the success of learning. This is in terms of developing positive attitudes towards the learning and assessment processes (Pransky and Bailey, 2009). Howard & Del Rosario have suggested that positive teacher attitudes are fostered in a culturally responsive learning environment and this facilitates and supports the success of the majority of learners (Howard & Del Rosario, 2000).

Though other factors such as intrinsic motivation of learners have been attributed to the success of the learners (Irvine, 2003), a culturally responsive environment also favors success as it instills a positive attitude in teachers towards teaching and the process of learning and assessment (Howard & Del Rosario, 2000). This is through the creation of an environment where learning is made intriguing and learners feel welcomed, supported, and provided with immense opportunities of learning in total disregard of cultural or linguistic inclinations (Pransky and Bailey, 2009).

Culturally, responsive teaching focuses on academic achievement, cultural competence, and socio-political consciousness which forms a conducive environment for schooling and learning and helps teachers develop attitudes that are motivating to their learners' thus favouring their academic success

and performance (Howard & Del Rosario, 2000; Irvine, 2003). It has also been suggested in other areas that teachers may sometimes suppress the learning and performance of some learners because of the basic reason that they subjectively feel that such learners cannot grasp such material in a manner that is as quick as the way other learners would. This attitude can be perceived in terms of aspects of bias which occurs when objective measures fail to show the differences which exist in terms of the potential of learning between learners expected to perform poorly as compared to other students in the same class (Swartz, 2003, Irvine, 2003).

According to Howard & Del Rosario (2000) and Forlenza, Bailey, & Shaw (1999), the most influential determinant of the academic performance of children is teacher quality and attitude, which is developed through effective teacher education programs that prepare prospective teachers who are highly qualified and focused on a culturally responsive pedagogy which is systematic and cohesive and runs through the entire curriculum. Howard and Del Rosario (2000) further assert that teacher educators who involve dialogue and give opportunities for obtaining competencies, skills, knowledge, and attitudes have recorded success as they train teachers who have achieved equity and excellence for many students in the education system and schools which have become culturally diverse.

Research has proven that teachers' attitudes which are shaped objectively have an upper hand in enhancing a successful and conducive learning environment and better performance of children. This is because such teachers have better knowledge of their children's world hence they work together with learners and open chances for learning success and better academic performance (Howard & Del Rosario, 2000; Pransky and Bailey, 2009).

According to Baker and Crist (1981), the likes and dislikes of teachers and what they appreciate including the feelings of students' learning and studies have a tremendous effect on the behavior and academic performance of students. This is despite the lack of realization among teachers that how they behave and teach and their interaction with learners are more important than what they teach. Thus, in summary, Baker and Crist (1981) assert that teachers' attitudes have a direct impact on the attitudes of their students and such attitudes are manifested through behavior. Therefore according to Baker and Crist, teachers' attitudes towards students affect the students' academic performance.

Research Methodology

The study utilized descriptive survey design. The researcher used this design in order to assemble information from a chosen populace with a point of deciding the present status of the chosen population in respect to a set of variables (Kothari, 2003). The descriptive survey design was further used to provide objectivity and in depth study within a limited time frame.

The investigation focused on 919 public pre-schools and 1,829 pre-primary teachers in Nandi County. The exploration focused on pre-school learners of public pre-primary two in the chosen pre-primary schools. The current research was grounded on Krejcie & Morgan (1970) cited by Kasomo (2001) sample size determination equation. The equation is given as:

$$n = \frac{X^2 * N * P(1 - P)}{(ME^2 * (N - 1)) + (X^2 * P * (1 - P))}$$

Where

n=Sample size

X^2 =Chi Square for the specified confidence level at 1 degree of freedom= (3.841)
 from tables
 N=Population size
 P=Population proportion (.50 in the table)
 ME=Desired margin of error (expressed as a proportion = 0.05)

Using the formula, the sample size for teachers was 160. The study used stratified random sampling to sample the public pre-primary schools. The strata were based on the sub-counties in Nandi County. The researcher stratified the public pre-primary schools into six sub-counties namely; Mosop, Emgwen, chesumei, Nandi Hills, Aldai and Tinderet. Thereafter, simple random sampling was used to select teachers who were going to get involved in the study from each of the sub-counties.

The sample frame and size of the study is summarized in table 1.

Table 1: Sampling Frame

Sub county	Number of teachers	Sample size of teachers
Emgwen	460	55
Mosop	176	18
Aldai	336	35
Nandi Hills	259	13
Tinderet	156	9
Chesumei	442	29
Total	1,829	160

Source: Nandi County Department of Education Office (2022)

The process of pre-testing the instrument was done in a neighbouring UasinGishu County outside the area of study but with similar conditions. The respondents were purposively selected from experienced teachers who were requested to comment on the relevance of the content, clarity of the questions, and the time taken to complete the questionnaire. The results from the piloting were incorporated in the final instruments' revisions and improve its content validity as well as questions, format and scales reliability (Ross, 2005).

The validity of the instruments was built up by means of the sort of material validity that included the assessment of the objects of the research instrument, for instance, the degree to which questions apply to the issues to be evaluated or the amount of information gathered using a specific point space or the substance of a particular idea (Mugenda&Mugenda, 2003). Validity also entails how adequate the items in a questionnaire provides information or content relevant to all objectives and how adequately the items enable the gathering of enough data for every objective in the study. Constructive criticisms, opinions and comments from other research experts were incorporated to the final data collection instrument which led to the restructuring of some items of the questionnaire which helped to strengthen the face and content validity of the instrument as recommended by Foxcroft, Wood, Kew, Herrington & Segal, (2004).

The qualitative data from the questionnaire was first subjected to preliminary processing through validation, coding tabulation in readiness for analysis with the assistance of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) computer package. Frequencies, percentages, mean and Standard deviation was used to analyze quantitative data.

Results

Analysis of the findings is categorized by the study objectives;

a) Strategies used by teachers in assessing learners

From the results, 128 (80%0 pre-school teachers agreed that assessment for learning is good strategy to be adopted as it is an investigative tool to monitor the progress of an individual learner in meeting the learning outcomes in a learning area. It involves gathering data during the learning process and provides feedback to both the learner and the teacher to help improve learning (KICD, 2017). This supports the finding of schellekens et. all (2021) who found in their study that assessment for learning is an approach to teaching and learning that creates feedback which is then used to improve learners' performance. Learners' become more involved in the learning process and from this gain confidence in what they are expected to learn and to what standard. Suskie, (2018) added that in order to determine whether the current instruction and intervention are having a positive impact on learner achievement or whether adjustments are necessary, frequent progress monitoring in which a learner's academic performance is frequently checked in between benchmarks is applied. From the respondents, 24(15%) agreed that assessment as learning is a method to be adopted which is a method that occurs when a learner is assisted to develop a capacity to be independent, self-directed to set individual goals, monitor own progress/self assess and reflect on one's learning. This helps the learner develop lifelong learning skills (learning to learn) (KICD, 2017). Teachers also encourage the learner to reflect on peer feedback, accommodate peer coaching as well as monitor the attainment of the set goals. This supports the finding of Junior (2020) who found that individuality should be maintained throughout the assessment process. Learners are better able to take ownership of their own learning and maintain track of their progress toward long-term objectives when assessments are integrated into the learning process (Wijnia&Baars, 2021) and 8(5%) agreed that assessment of learning is to be used as it is designed to provide information on the achievement of a learner to parents, educators and learners themselves (KICD, 2017). These findings concur with those of Voinea (2018), that every learner's performance on a set of learning tasks and activities can be captured in a single moment in time by a teacher, learner or parent conducting a learning assessment.

The first objective was to establish strategies used by teachers in assessing learners' environmental performance in preschools. The study found that most teachers adopted the assessment for learning strategy to promote the acquisition of various competencies and skills by learners despite their learning ability at the pre-primary level.

b) Teachers training level towards assessment

From the study findings, 90% of the teachers agreed that teacher training is a significant determinant of learners' assessment thus their achievement in the acquisition of various competencies. This is supported by Aggarwal, (2014), who noted that the teacher is a permanent individual in the teaching and learning process because the teacher creates the learning situation for the learners, i.e. the process is the interaction between the learner and the teacher. Teaching –learning process is influenced by the totality of the situation i.e. it is fruitful and permanent if the total situation is related to real-life situation. Teachers can play an important role in facilitating learning when they take into account the needs of the learners in a holistic manner.

Hattie (2009), his review on research on the factors that affect learner achievement, all agree that teachers make by far the biggest difference to learner achievement. They have even qualified this, and

conclude that teachers have three to four times the effect on achievement of any other school or college factors. This is advanced by the “proximity effect”, that is, the closer you are to the learner, the greater your effect on their achievement. Leech (2005), added that the quality of observation and subsequent assessment of learners of children’s development and learning depends very much on skills of the individual practitioner. If assessments are going to be worthwhile, meeting individual children’s needs and providing information for the future planning of activities and experiences, they should consequently be of the highest possible quality. Practitioners should ensure that children make progress and that recognition is given to their achievements.

The study also established that 10% of teachers never saw that need of training being a prerequisite of carrying out learner assessment at the pre-primary level.

The second research objective was to examine teachers training level towards assessment on learner’s environmental activities. From the findings, despite teachers agreeing that is a significant determinant of learners’ assessment, it revealed that most teachers consisting of 70% had not gone back for training in the various institutions within the country to undertake the new system of curriculum, that is, Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) which is also giving new methods of assessment techniques in line with the trends of education which is embracing the development of skills among the learners in environmental activities at the preschool level.

c) Teacher’s motivation as a factor which affect the teachers’ attitude towards

Motivation being an indispensable condition for teaching, it energizes and accelerates the behavior of a teacher. Desirable changes in a teacher’s behavior are only possible when he or she is properly motivated. No teaching is possible without motivation (Aggarwal, 2014). Due to this fact, from the study findings 152 (95%) of teachers concurred that motivation should be enhanced by concerned personnel to teachers as it leads directly to their assessment activities on learners environmental activities, this is because at any given time teachers vary in the extent to which they are willing to direct their energies to the attainment of goals, due to variations in individual levels of motivation. This supports the findings of Aggarwal , (2014) who asserted that the teacher must be interested in what he is teaching and in the children who he is teaching. If this is not so, he or she can never motivate the class. It may be said that a teacher who has been teaching the same activity areas to the same classes for years tends to lose interest. This is not factually correct. The subject-matter may be the same, but the children are not. Even the subject-matter itself is always changing and developing. Moreover, with experience, the teacher will discover new approaches and methods of teaching even the same subject-matter. This would challenge and motivate the teacher, which might explain why some teachers improve in their teaching skills over the years. The study established that 8(5%) of teachers agreed that teacher motivation isn’t a necessity for one to carry out learners assessment in the teaching and learning process.

The third research objective was to evaluate teachers’ motivation as a factor which affects teacher’s attitude towards assessment on learner’s environmental activities performance in preschools. From the findings, most teachers had a positive attitude towards learner’s assessment despite working in environments that were not very conducive i.e. lack of good infrastructure and teaching resources in most of the pre-schools.

d) Support provided by administrators towards assessment

Ninety six (96) percent of teachers acknowledge that the support provided to them by administrators in their pre-schools boost their assessment procedure being carried out in the various learning areas.

Wahlstrom and Louis (2008) found that the effects of principal leadership on instruction were relatively weak, but that the perception of teachers regarding principal leadership had a significant effect on the degree to which teachers engage in particular instructional practices.

Poeret.all (2016) pointed out that when learners are provided with the required strategies and skills they will be more responsible in their daily lives, both in and out of the classroom and school environment.

Busher et.al (2015) stated that the essential task for schools is to guide learners to achieve the organized goals. Thus, an effective and successful school can be defined as learners having acquired the goals planned for them and 4% teachers disagreed with the statement that is they believe that own efforts should propel learners academic achievement.

The last objective was to explore support provided by administrators towards assessment of learners environmental. From the findings, administrators support was not a guaranteed at the preschool level, claiming the fact that there is no good support from the county government in terms of finances because preschools are under the county government management. This has led to limited teachers' participation in assessment strategies towards the preschoolers. This is also aggravated by the fact that preschools teachers' terms of services have not been unified among the county governments thus making teachers to be demotivated which is affecting their delivering of services in terms of assessment at the preschool level.

Conclusion

The study concludes that teachers had a positive attitude towards learner's assessment of environmental activities. However, limitation came in terms of teachers not fully equipped on the new system of curriculum, that is, Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) leading to having inadequate knowledge on the Competence Based Curriculum assessment techniques, administrators support was also limited which affected teachers execution of the assessment exercise towards learners to experience success in the various activities they engage in both inside and outside the classroom during environmental activities lessons.

Recommendations

The study recommend that the county government should escalate their support towards preschool education through the school administrators to ensure that all procedures are well undertaken to ensure that learners experience success before they move from one level of education to the next level of education in their education ladder.

Teachers should be sensitized to get the required knowledge pertaining the advantages that led the government to embrace the Competence Based Curriculum system of education so that they can see the need to go back for further training to gain new skills that will boost their delivery of services at the preschool level in terms of assessment techniques to be used for learners to experience success in environmental activities. This will also boost the teachers' motivation towards their career so as to ensure that they provide equal assessment opportunities to all learners under care so that they can exploit that talents and potential which will lead them to the right career pathway later in life to ensure that they fulfill their dreams in life.

In the most effective settings practitioners support and challenge learners thinking by getting involved in the thinking process with them. The adults' should show genuine interest, offer encouragement,

clarifies ideas and asks questions. This support extends children's thinking and helps to make connections in learning.

In order for assessment to capture a picture of the whole child, the teacher needs to ensure that they incorporate as many views in the process as possible. This might include staff from the previous setting a child has attended, teaching assistants, welfare staff, outside agencies e.g. special therapists, health visitor, educational psychologist, learning support staff etc.

The child's parents will have vital information to contribute since they know the child better than anyone else, and of course not forgetting the child him/herself.

For successful Competence Based Curriculum assessment results, the government through the Ministry of Education needs to provide resources such as learning resources, offering regular and comprehensive Competence Based Curriculum training, sensitize teachers and the public on the importance of the Competence Based Curriculum offer adequate and more training on Competence Based Curriculum assessment and provision of all required learning material.

The government through the ministry of education and education stakeholders to sensitize the public on Competence Based Curriculum, also sensitize parents on the importance of parental involvement in Competence Based Curriculum education, and fund continuous professional development training in schools, to equip teachers with knowledge on various aspects of Competence Based Curriculum.

Extensive teacher training both at the college level and inform with Continuous Professional Development (CPD) in Competence Based Curriculum is recommended. The ministry of education should also take careful consideration while allocating resources including teaching staff should be adopted.

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